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Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>*Research Article***DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF ORAL DISINTEGRATING
TABLETS OF KETOTIFEN****Ramavth Govind*¹, Dr. K. Shrivankumar, Dr.K. Chaitanyaprasad, Dr.B. Sudhakar.**
Department Of Pharmaceutics, Samskruti College Of Pharmacy In Ghatkesar, Telangana.
501301.**Abstract:**

The present study was carried out to develop Oral Disintegration Tablets of Ketotifen. Primojel, PEG 8000 and Croscarmellose sodium were used as super disintegrants. The drug –excipients interaction was investigated by FTIR. The blend of all the formulations showed good flow properties such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density. The prepared tablets were shown good post compression parameters and they passed all the quality control evaluation parameters as per I.P limits. Among all the formulations F9 showed maximum % drug release i.e., 99.01% in 30 min hence it is considered as optimized formulation.

Keywords : Ketotifen, Primojel, PEG 8000, Croscarmellose sodium and Oral disintegrating tablets.

Corresponding author:**Ramavth Govind*.**

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Samskruti College Of Pharmacy,
Ghatkesar, Telangana.

Email Id- govindharamavath@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Formulation of drugs into a presentable form is the basic requirement and need of today. Dosage form is a mean of drug delivery system, used for the application of drug to a living body. Various type of dosage forms are available such as tablets, syrups, suspensions, suppositories, injections, transdermal and patches having different type of drug delivery mechanisms. These classical/modern dosage forms have some advantages and disadvantages therefore the development of an ideal drug delivery system is a big challenge to the pharmacist in the presence scenario. In order to get the desired effect the drug should be delivered to its site of action at such rate and concentration to achieve the maximum therapeutic effect and minimum adverse effect. For the development of a suitable dosage form a thorough study about the physicochemical principles that governs a specific formulation of a drug should be subjected¹.

During establishing dosage form for a drug, it requires knowledge about each ingredient i.e. physical, chemical and biological properties along with the compatibility with the active drug, so that the product formed should be palatable, stable and efficacious. Most drugs pass through the barrier by molecular diffusion, or through pores called pore diffusion. In pore diffusion the drug release rate is controlled by the crystal size, molecular size, pore size, pore structure and tortuosity of the polymers. In passive transport (Fick's first law) the drug moves from high concentration to the low concentration, while in active transport energy is required for the movement of drug from low to high concentration region through one or more transport mechanisms. It requires energy or carrier such as enzyme, protein².

Need Of Innovative Drug Delivery System

The orally administered drug delivery is still considered as a standard system in pharmaceuticals field and still considered safest, convenient and economical method of administration providing best route for patient compliance³, however in case of tablet and capsule having a common drawback of difficulty in swallowing leading to poor compliance specially in geriatrics⁴.

To improve compliance and making the administration convenient, design of new dosage forms gained significant importance. Conventional oral drug delivery present a drug with quick and full release that may go as such without producing the desired effect may be due to the presence of food, pH of the stomach, enzymatic degradation, change in GIT

motility as so forth, giving not enough time to get absorbed⁵. Recently much light is being put on the area of designing drug delivery systems bearing organoleptic elegance and maximum patient acceptability in pediatrics and geriatric groups^{6,7,8}. A lot of innovative work is being done on drug delivery in which oral route is preferred because of ease of administration, cost effective therapy, self medication and noninvasive method leading to patient compliance to a higher level. Tablet coating is one of the parameter in drug delivery designing applied to minimize the bad tasting and side effects while enhancing elegance and drug bioavailability⁹.

Oral Disintegrating Tablets

Drinking water is mostly required for the oral administration of drugs, like tablet and capsules, in which some patients experience nuisance in swallowing bulky conventional dosage forms¹⁰. In order to prevent the dysphagia and improve patient compliance, orodispersible tablets are introduced as a substitute in oral DDS, designed to disintegrate in mouth without the aid of water. So they are useful in such conditions in which water is not available, or prohibited as before operation, in kinetosis, cough episodes due to neurological stimulation or chest infections. Different methods are adopted to manufacture the orodispersible tablets with the aim of giving fast disintegration to the dosage form as it gets in contact with saliva with good agreeable mouth feeling¹¹. These orodispersible tablets (ODT) can be administered to any patients having difficulty in swallowing. They are also recognized as mouth dissolvable, melt-in-mouth, fast dissolving, rapi-melts or porous tablets¹².

These are tablets which get dispersed or disintegrate when gets in a contact with saliva with the release of active drug, providing maximum drug bioavailability as compared to conventional dosage form. This dispersible property is given by the addition of superdisintegrants to the dosage form, that releases the drug in mouth increasing the bioavailability¹³. Three different methods for the addition of disintegrants are used, they are intra granular (within the granules), extra granular (addition after granulation) and combination of both processes¹⁴.

The best time for an orodispersible tablet to get disperse is considered to be less than a minute. Mostly the disintegration times varies from 5 to 30 seconds and are prepared applying; direct compression, solid dispersion, lyophilization or molding techniques. In all these methods direct compression is preferred because of its effortlessness, quick procedure and cost effectiveness¹⁵. ODTs are developed by the addition

of super disintegrants like cross linked cellulose derivative; carboxymethyl cellulose, sodium starch glycolate, polyvinylpyrrolidone, which gives burst disintegration when gets in contact with water or salivary secretions. Bioavailability of drugs may rise due to oral and pregastric absorption, reducing first pass metabolism in gastrointestinal tract¹⁶

Oral drug delivery is currently the gold standard in the pharmaceutical industry where it is regarded as the safest, the most convenient and most economical method of drug delivery with the highest patient compliance¹⁷. Oral route is the most preferred route of administration and tablet and capsules are the most preferred dosage forms, but several limitations of that kind of dosage forms like choking and swelling discomfort in geriatric and pediatric patients^{18,19}. Orally disintegrating tablets have been developed and new ODT technologies compensate many pharmaceuticals and patients' needs, ranging from enhanced life-cycle management to convenient dosing for pediatric, geriatric, and psychiatric patients with dysphasia. Over the past three decades, orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) have gained considerable attention as a preferred alternative to conventional tablets and capsules due to better patient compliance²⁰. ODTs are being named as orodispersible, rapid-dissolving, mouth-dissolving, rapid-disintegrating tablets. There are some definitions that made by pharmacopeias and agency as follows: Orodispersible tablets have been placed in the mouth where they disperse fast before being swallowed and they are uncoated tablets. Orodispersible tablets disintegrate within 180 seconds when the disintegration tests have been conducted up to the test for disintegration of tablets^{21,22}. Orally disintegrating tablets are intended to disintegrate fast in the mouth to provide dispersion before being swallowed where the active ingredient is intended for gastrointestinal delivery and/or absorption. A solid dosage form containing active ingredients which disintegrates fast, usually within seconds, when put on the tongue. In addition to those definitions, FDA recommends that, orally disintegrating tablets should be considered as solid oral preparations that disintegrate fast in mouth, with an in-vitro disintegration time of approximately less than or equal to 30 seconds, when the disintegration test conducted to the United States Pharmacopeia (USP) disintegration test method or alternative²³.

Bioequivalence

Bioequivalence of ODTs has some challenges but in this part basic solutions to overcome these challenges were given. Active pharmaceutical ingredients that are formulated as ODTs should be dispersed or dissolved

in the saliva, then directly absorbed via oral mucosa and/or absorbed through the gastrointestinal system. When defining the dissolution test conditions to prove both of the in-vitro and in-vivo bioequivalence of two formulations, the physiological conditions of the mouth should be considered. pH, flow rate, volume of the saliva and targeted population are the important factors that should be considered. There are several in-vivo studies for ODTs that conducted to prove bioequivalence of the ODTs, nevertheless BCS based biowaiver is also being considered for especially the active pharmaceutical ingredients are not absorbed via oral mucosa, but must be absorbed through the gastrointestinal system. But if this cannot be demonstrated, bioequivalence must be evaluated via in-vivo studies. If the ODT test product is an extension to another oral formulation, a 3-period study is recommended in order to evaluate administration of the orodispersible tablet both with and without concomitant fluid intake. However, if bioequivalence between ODT taken without water and reference formulation with water is demonstrated in a 2-period study, bioequivalence of ODT taken with water can be assumed. If the ODT is a generic/hybrid to an approved ODT reference medicinal product, the following recommendations regarding study design apply:

- If the reference medicinal product can be taken with or without water, bioequivalence should be demonstrated without water as this condition best resembles the intended use of the formulation. This is especially important if the substance may be dissolved and partly absorbed in the oral cavity. If bioequivalence is demonstrated when taken without water, also bioequivalence can be assumed with ODT taken with water.
- If the reference medicinal product is taken only in one way (e.g. only with water), bioequivalence should be shown in this condition (in a conventional two-way crossover design).
- If the reference medicinal product is taken only in one way (e.g. only with water), and the test product is intended for additional ways of administration (e.g. without water), the conventional and the new method should be compared with the reference in the conventional way of administration (3 treatment, 3 period, 6 sequence design). In studies evaluating ODTs without water, it is recommended to wet the mouth by swallowing 20 ml of water directly before applying the ODT on the tongue. It is recommended not to allow fluid intake earlier than 1 hour after administration.²⁴

Advantages of ODTs

The major advantage of the ODT formulation is that it combines the advantages of both liquid and

conventional tablet formulations. It provides the convenience of a tablet formulation, and also allows the ease of swallowing as the liquid formulation. Others are:

- ✓ Not requirement of water or other liquid to swallow.
- ✓ Easily dissolution or disintegration in saliva within a few seconds.
- ✓ Pleasing taste.
- ✓ Leave in trace amount or no residue in the mouth when administered.
- ✓ Being portable and easy to transport.
- ✓ Being able to be manufactured by direct compression method with low cost.
- ✓ Can be easily administered to children, old and mentally disabled patients.
- ✓ Accurate dosing as compared to liquids.
- ✓ Dissolution and absorption of drug is fast, offering rapid onset of action.
- ✓ Bioavailability of drug is increased as some drugs are absorbed from mouth, pharynx and esophagus through saliva transferring down into the stomach.
- ✓ First pass metabolism is reduced, thus offering improved bioavailability and thus reduced dose and side effects.
- ✓ Free from risk of suffocation due to physical obstruction when swallowed, thus offering improved safety.
- ✓ Suitable for sustained/controlled release actives.
- ✓ Allows high drug loading²⁵⁻²⁸.

Challenges and Limitations for ODTs

Drugs with relatively larger doses are difficult to formulate into ODTs e.g. antibiotics like ciprofloxacin with adult dose tablet containing about 500 mg of the drug. The application for technologies used for ODTs is limited by the amount of drug into each unit dose. The drug dose must be lower than 400mg for insoluble drugs and 60mg for soluble drugs²⁹.

However Flashdose technology can accommodate larger drug doses and offers improved mechanical strength. Orasolv® technology can accommodate a wide range of active pharmaceutical ingredient from 1 mg to 500 mg.

- ✓ **Mechanical strength** - ODTs are made of porous or soft molded matrices in order to allow its disintegration in mouth. This makes tablet friable and handling becomes difficult. Orodispersible tablets with highly porous structure and good mechanical strength have been developed by sublimation method. Also Durasolv® has much higher mechanical strength than Orasolv due to the use of higher compaction pressures during compression.

- ✓ **Palatability** - ODTs are intended to be dissolved in mouth. Most of the drugs have bitter taste. Bitter taste can be masked with enough sweetener and flavors. Specifically, methods of taste masking include lipophilic vehicles, coating with polymers, carbohydrates, lipids or proteins complexation with cyclodextrins or ion-exchange resins, formation of salts, use of salting out layers and solid dispersions. OraQuick utilizes its own patented taste masking technology i.e. MicroMask®. In MicroMask® technology, taste-masking process is done by incorporating drug into matrix microsphere.
- ✓ Drugs in form of ODTs are hygroscopic in nature and hence need to be protected from humidity. To overcome humidity problem special working facilities can be designed by simple methods and special air-conditioning systems can be set up.
- ✓ Size of tablet 7 and 8 mm are easy to swallow while tablets of size 8mm are easy to handle. Hence, tablet sizes which are both easy to handle and swallow are difficult to achieve. For the patient compliance, to make the swallowing easier, round shape punches having optimum dimensions can be used.
- ✓ Drug candidates should be stable both in water and in saliva, should not ionize at oral cavity pH and should be able to permeate oral mucosal tissue to diffuse and partition in upper GI epithelium ($\log P > 1$, or preferably > 2 , not have short half-life). To optimize solubility problem of the active pharmaceutical ingredient some solid buffers and surfactants can also be chosen.³⁰

Future of ODTs

- ✓ ODT technology is applicable to a wide range of therapeutic agents including gene rics, thereby adding value, i.e. "supergenerics" for veterinary or human application.
- ✓ Some new quality control methods can be developed to determine the technological aspects of orally disintegrating tablets to define the characteristics of ODTs.
- ✓ Protein and peptide-based therapeutics that used via oral route, have limited bioavailability when administered by immediate release tablets. Those kinds of products usually degrade immediately in gastrointestinal system. The developments of improved oral protein delivery Technology by ODTs, that dispersed and/or dissolved in the saliva, are very promising for the delivery of high molecular weight protein and peptide.
- ✓ It would be an innovative improvement in the ODT technology when development of ODTs with controlled release properties that can deliver drugs which has short half-lives like 12–24 hours.

The added convenience and compliance of such formulations will be used more immensely .

- ✓ In addition, the ability to formulate drugs in large doses will bring another important technological advance. In general, the ODT formulations require large amounts of excipients, and having large doses of drug will only make the final formulation too big to handle. ODT formulations that require fewer excipients than the drug itself will be a break through .
- ✓ ODT technologies are in progress, but development of formulation of ODTs that contains lipophilic active pharmaceutical ingredients is a challenge. New ODT technology should be developed to find a solution for this problem .

As far as seen in the literature there is not much delayed release ODTs in the market. Controlled release ODTs and/or in line with the purpose system and/or fixed dose combination ODT technologies can be developed as a next generation.

MATERIALS

Ketotifen-Procured From Modi- Mundipharma Private Ltd(U.P,India) Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, Primojel-SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, PEG 8000-SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, Croscarmellose sodium-SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, Sodium saccharin- SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, Talc-SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, Magnesium stearate-SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, Microcrystalline cellulose SD Fine Chemicals Ltd.

METHODOLOGY:

Characterization of Ketotifen

Organoleptic properties:

Take a small quantity of sample and spread it on the white paper and examine it visually for color, odour and texture.

Determination of Ketotifen Melting point

The melting point of Ketotifen was determined by capillary tube method according to the USP. A sufficient quantity of Ketotifen powder was introduced into the capillary tube to give a compact column of 4-6 mm in height. The tube was introduced in electrical melting point apparatus and the temperature was raised. The melting point was recorded, which is the temperature at which the last solid particle of Ketotifen in the tube passed into liquid phase.

Determination of Ketotifen Solubility

Determination of solubility of drug by visual observation. An excess quantity of Ketotifen was taken separately and add in 10 ml of different solutions. These solutions were shaken well for few minutes.

Then the solubility was observed and observations are shown in the Table.

Buffer preparation:

Preparation of 0.2 M Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate solution: Accurately weighed 27.128 gm of monobasic potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 1000 ml of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide solution : Accurately weighed 8 gm of sodium hydroxide pellets were dissolved in 1000 mL of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer : Accurately measured 250 mL of 0.2 M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and 112.5 mL of 0.2 M NaOH was taken into the 1000 mL volumetric flask. Volume was made up to 1000 mL with distilled water.

Analytical method development for Ketotifen:

a) Determination of absorption maxima

A spectrum of the working standards was obtained by scanning from 200-400 nm against the reagent blank to fix absorption maxima. The λ_{max} was found to be 252nm. Hence all further investigations were carried out at the same wavelength.

b) Construction of standard graph

100 mg of Ketotifen was dissolved in 100 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to give a concentration in 1mg/mL (1000 μ g/mL) 10 ml was taken and diluted to 100 ml with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to give a concentration of 0.1 mg/ml (100 μ g/ml). From this stock solution aliquots of 0.5 ml, 1 ml, 1.5 ml, 2.0 ml, 2.5 ml, were pipette out in 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to produce concentration of 5,10,15,20 and 25 μ g/ml respectively. The absorbance of each concentration was measured at respective (λ_{max}) i.e., 252nm.

Preformulation parameters

Pre compression parameters:

Measurement of Micromeritic properties of powders

1.Angle of repose

The angle of repose of API powder is determined by the funnel method. The accurately weighed powder blend is taken in the funnel. The height of the funnel is adjusted in a way that the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the powder blend. The powder blend is allowed to flow through the funnel freely on the surface . The diameter of the powder cone is measured and angle of repose is calculated using the following equation.

$$\tan \Theta = h/r \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where , h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

Table 9.1: Flow Properties and Corresponding Angle Of Repose

Flow Property	Angle of Repose (°)
Excellent	25-30
Good	31-35
Fair- aid not needed	36-40
Passable-may hang up	41-45
Poor-must agitate, Vibrate	46-55
Very Poor	56-65
Very, very Poor	>66

2. Bulk density

The powder sample under test is screened through sieve No.18 and the sample equivalent to 25 gm is weighed and filled in 100 ml graduated cylinder and the powder is leveled and the unsettled volume, V_0 is noted. The bulk density is calculated in g/cm^3 by the formula.

$$\text{Bulk density} = M/V_0 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

V_0 = apparent unsettled volume

M= Powder mass

3. Tapped density

The powder sample under test is screened through sieve No. 18 and the weight of the sample equivalent to 25 gm filled in 100ml graduated cylinder. The mechanical tapping of cylinder is carried out using tapped density tester at a nominal rate for 500 times initially and the tapped volume V_0 is noted. Tappings are proceeded further for an additional tapping 750 times and tapped volume, V_b is noted. The difference between two tapping volume is < 2%, V_b is considered

as a tapped volume V_f . The tapped density is calculated in g/cm^3 by the formula.

$$\text{Tapped density} = M/V_f \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

M = weight of sample powder taken

V_f = Tapped volume

4. Compressibility index

The compressibility index of the powder blend is determined by Carr's index to know the flow character of a powder. This formula for Carr's index is as below:

$$\text{Carr's Index (\%)} = [(TD-BD)/TD] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

5. Hausner's ratio

The Hausner's ratio is a number that is correlated to the flowability of a powder or granular material. The ratio of tapped density to bulk density of the powders is called the Hausner's ratio. It is calculated by the following equation.

$$H = \rho_T / \rho_B \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

where ρ_T = tapped density, ρ_B = bulk density

Table 9.2 : Scale of Flowability

Compressibility index (%)	Flow character	Hausner Ratio
≤ 10	Excellent	1.00-1.11
11-15	Good	1.12-1.18
16-20	Fair	1.19-1.25
21-25	Passable	1.26-1.34
26-31	Poor	1.35-1.45
32-37	Very Poor	1.46-1.59
> 38	Very, very Poor	> 1.60

Drug-Excipients compatibility studies:

Drug excipients compatibility studies were carried out by mixing the drug with various excipients in different proportions (in 1:1 ratio were to have maximum likelihood interaction between them) was placed in a vial, and closed with rubber stopper and sealed properly. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) studies were performed on drug, optimized formulation using Bruker FTIR. The samples were analyzed between wave numbers 4000 cm^{-1} and 550 cm^{-1} .

Preparation of ODT Ketotifen:

Drug and different concentrations of (Primojel, PEG 8000 and Croscarmellose sodium) and

required ingredients were accurately weighed and passed through a 40-mesh screen to get uniform size particles and mixed in a glass mortar for 15 min.

- The obtained blend was lubricated with magnesium stearate and glidant Talc was added and mixing was continued for further 5 min.
- The blend was evaluated for the following pre compression parameters.
- The resultant mixture was directly compressed into tablets by using punch of rotary tablet compression machine.

Compression force was kept constant for all formulations.

Table 9.3 : Formulation table showing various compositions

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CODE								
	F1 (mg)	F2 (mg)	F3 (mg)	F4 (mg)	F5 (mg)	F6 (mg)	F7 (mg)	F8 (mg)	F9 (mg)
Ketotifen	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Primojel	20	40	60	-	-	-	-	-	-
PEG 8000	-	-	-	20	40	60	-	-	-
Croscarmellose sodium	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	40	60
Sodium saccharin	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Magnesium stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Microcrystalline cellulose 102	87	67	47	87	67	47	87	67	47
Total weight (mg)	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The tablets were prepared by using tablet compression machine. The hardness of the tablet was maintained as (3.0 - 4.6) kg/cm²

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Organoleptic properties

Table 10.1: Organoleptic properties

S NO.	Properties	Results
1	State	solid
2	Colour	white
3	Odour	Odourless
4	Melting point	193°C

Solubility studies

Table 10.2: Solubility studies of drug in different solvents

S NO.	Solvents	Solubility of Ketotifen
1	Water	Freely soluble
2	Methanol	sparingly soluble
3	Acetone	freely soluble
4	Alcohol	soluble

Preparation of calibration curve of Ketotifen:

The regression coefficient was found to be 0.999 which indicates a linearity with an equation of $y=0.036x$. Hence Beer-Lambert's law was obeyed.

Table 10.3: Calibration curve data of Ketotifen in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.168
10	0.376
15	0.547
20	0.742
25	0.914

Figure 10.1 : Calibration curve data of Ketotifen in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

FTIR RESULTS:

Figure 10.2 : FTIR of Ketotifen Pure Drug

Fig 10.3 : FTIR of Ketotifen optimized formulation

From the above studies it was found that there was no shifting in the major peaks which indicated that there were no significant interactions occurred between the Ketotifen and excipients used in the preparation of different Ketotifen Oral disintegrating tablets formulations. Therefore the drug and excipients are compatible to form stable

Formulations under study, The FTIR spectra of Ketotifen and physical mixture used for optimized formulation were obtained and these are depicted in above figures. From the FTIR data it was evident that the drug and excipients does not have any interactions. Hence they were compatible.

EVALUATION OF PRE-COMPRESION PARAMETERS OF POWDER BLEND

Table 10.4 : Evaluation of pre-compression parameters of powder blend

Formulation code	Angle of repose	Bulk density(gm/mL)	Tapped density (gm/mL)	Carr's index(%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	35.6±0.12	0.85±0.13	0.98±0.10	13.6	1.16
F2	34.1±0.12	0.89±0.13	0.93±0.10	14.3	1.17
F3	27.3±0.15	0.96±0.12	0.98±0.10	12.6	1.11
F4	29.2±0.09	0.82±0.11	0.95±0.12	06.6	1.07
F5	31.6±0.12	0.85±0.12	0.94±0.10	11.9	1.13
F6	25.3±0.12	0.89±0.15	0.93±0.14	14.3	1.17
F7	29.6±0.13	0.94±0.10	0.95±0.13	15.1	1.18
F8	27.3±0.15	0.96±0.12	0.98±0.10	12.6	1.11
F9	29±0.10	0.91±0.10	0.89±0.09	10.9	1.12

- For each formulation blend of drug and excipients were prepared and evaluated for various pre compression parameters described earlier in methodology chapter.
- The bulk density of all formulations was found in the range of 0.82 ± 0.11 - 0.96 ± 0.12 and tapped density was in the range of 0.89 ± 0.09 - 0.98 ± 0.10
- The Carr's index and Hausner's ratio was calculated from tapped density and bulk density.

EVALUATIONS OF POST COMPRESSION PARAMETERS OF KETOTIFEN ODTs

Table 10.5 : Evaluation of post compression parameters of Ketotifen Oral Disintegrating Tablets

Formulation codes	Average weight(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	<i>In vitro</i> disintegration Time (sec)
F1	118.3	3.0	0.63	2.5	97.20	25
F2	117.4	3.5	0.55	2.4	97.19	19
F3	119.8	4.6	0.50	2.5	97.99	31
F4	119.5	3.1	0.49	2.2	97.56	46
F5	120.7	3.2	0.34	2.6	98.14	20
F6	119.3	3.0	0.59	2.5	99.10	33
F7	118.5	4.5	0.41	2.0	97.05	52
F8	120.8	3.0	0.38	2.3	97.25	47
F9	118.1	3.8	0.40	2.4	98.56	16

Weight variation and Thickness : All the formulations were evaluated for uniformity of weight using electronic weighing balance and the results are shown above. The average tablet weights of all the formulations were noted down.

Hardness and friability: All the ODT formulations were evaluated for their hardness using Monsanto hardness tester and the results are shown above. The average hardness for all formulations was found to be between (3.0 - 4.6) kg/cm² which was found to be acceptable. Friability was determined to evaluate the ability of the tablets to withstand the abrasion during packing, handling and transpoting. All the ODT formulations were evaluated for their percentage friability using Roche friabilator and the results are shown above. The average percentage friability for all the formulations was between 0.34-0.63 which was found to be within the limit.

Drug content : All formulations were evaluated for drug content according to the procedure described in methodology section and the results were shown above . The assay values for all formulations were found to be in the range of (97.05 -99.10). According to IP standards the tablets must contain not less than 95% and not more than 105% of the stated amount of the drug. Thus, all the ODT formulation comply with the standards given in IP.

***In vitro* Disintegration time :** *In vitro* disintegration studies showed from 16-52 Sec. The F9 formulation showed *in vitro* disintegration time i.e 16 sec.

Figure 10.4 : *In vitro* disintegration Time (sec)**IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES OF ORALLY DISINTEGRATING TABLETS**

Table 10.6 : Dissolution data of Ketotifen

TIME (MIN)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	58.76	59.22	63.54	48.32	51.43	54.6	55.36	58.95	63.54
10	64.93	66.31	74.19	57.23	62.19	67.15	65.89	66.55	74.19
15	70.32	78.24	82.37	72.33	76.67	79.81	78.36	79.34	82.37
20	78.17	83.67	87.25	79.51	85.46	89.36	81.28	85.18	88.25
30	89.62	92.39	94.98	84.77	89.73	92.47	88.76	91.24	99.01

Figure 10.5 : Dissolution profile of formulations F1, F2, F3

Figure 10.6 : Dissolution profile of formulations F4, F5, F6

Figure 10.7 : Dissolution profile of formulations F7, F8, F9

Figure 10.8 : Dissolution profile of all formulations F1-F9

From the Table it was evident that the formulations prepared with Primojel powder were showed good drug release i.e., 94.98 % (F3 Formulation) in higher concentration of blend i.e. 60mg. Formulations prepared with PEG 8000 showed good drug release i.e., 92.47 % (F6 Formulation) in 60 mg concentration when increase in the concentration of Croscarmellose sodium drug release was retarded. Formulations prepared with Croscarmellose sodium showed maximum drug release i.e., 99.01% (F9 Formulation) at 30 min in 60 mg of blend.

Among all formulations F9 formulation considered as optimised formulation which showed maximum drug release at 30 min. i.e. 99.01 %. Croscarmellose sodium were showed good release when compared to other disintegrating.

Finally concluded that F9 formulation (contains Croscarmellose sodium) was optimised better formulation.

CONCLUSION:

In the present work, an attempt has been made to develop Oral disintegrating tablets of Ketotifen. Primojel, PEG 8000 and Croscarmellose sodium were used as super disintegrants. FTIR study reveals that there is no drug-excipients interaction between Ketotifen and excipients. The blend of all formulations showed good flow properties such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density. The prepared tablets were shown good post compression parameters and they passed all the quality control evaluation parameters as per I.P limits.

From the Dissolution data it was evident that the formulations prepared with Croscarmellose sodium were showed good drug release i.e., 99.01% (F9) in higher concentration of blend i.e., 60mg. Among all formulations F9 formulation was considered as optimized formulation which showed maximum drug release at 30 min i.e., 99.01%. Finally concluded that F9 Formulation (containing Croscarmellose sodium) was optimized better formulation.

FUTURE SCOPE

There are several biopharmaceutical advantages such as improved efficiency over conventional dosage forms for Fast disintegrating tablets. For example, they require smaller amounts of active ingredient to be effective, improve absorption profiles, and offer better drug bioavailability than regular tablets and capsules. There are still many aspects to improve in the ODT formulations. The disintegration times of most ODTs on the market are acceptable i.e., less than 60 seconds

but certainly there is a room for improvement. Because the disintegration time is related to other formulation variables, a balance has to be maintained between shortening the disintegration time and other tablet properties. The tablet stability can be further improved to such a level that multi-tablet packaging in conventional bottles becomes a norm. There may be no magic solution to this, but more effective use of existing taste masking technologies is expected to alleviate the problems associated with taste masking. The future of ODTs lies in the development of FDTs with controlled release properties. The safety and efficacy profile of drugs in ODT tablet is same like their conventional tablet dosage form. Based on conventional techniques, new techniques are developed like Zydis, Wow Tab, Flashtab technology and many more, which leads to getting a patent and new market strategy for ODT. This dosage form are gaining market share day by day and becoming a better choice of acceptance.

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